

Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization and X-ray analysis of racemic 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile

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Abstract : The present communication deals with the eco-friendly synthesis, spectral properties and X-ray crystal structure of an α -amino acid, 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile (**1**). The title compound (m.f. C₁₄H₁₀ClFN₂) crystallizes in the orthorhombic space group Pbcn with the unit-cell parameters : $a = 13.9791(4)$, $b = 6.9972(2)$, $c = 25.0724(6)$ Å and $Z = 8$. The crystal structure was solved by direct methods using single-crystal X-ray diffraction data collected at room temperature and refined by full-matrix least-squares procedures to a final R -value of 0.0494 for 1992 observed reflections. The molecule is organized in the crystal lattice forming interpenetrating layers. Weak intermolecular van der Waals interactions are responsible for the stability of molecules in the unit cell.

Keywords : α -Aminonitrile, catalyst and solvent-free synthesis, Strecker reaction, no column chromatography, spectral properties, crystal structure, single-crystal, direct method.

Introduction

α -Aminonitriles are considered as key prebiotic precursors to porphyrins, corrins, nicotinic acids, and nucleic acids¹, and find wide applications in the synthesis of potentially active natural and unnatural molecules of pharmacological interest². They are also regarded as versatile intermediates for the preparation of nitrogen and sulfur-containing heterocycles, such as imidazoles and thiadiazoles³. Furthermore, α -aminonitriles are the key precursors of diverse α -amino acids used to synthesize many proteins⁴, and are also chiral building blocks in the pharmaceutical industry⁵. Such valuable organic intermediates play a key role in the synthesis of several lead molecules such as clopidogrel^{2,6}, manzacidin A-C⁷, prasugrel⁸, saframycin A⁹, ecteinascidin 743¹⁰, and phthalascidin¹¹. α -Aminonitriles can easily be accessed via Strecker reaction¹² from carbonyl compounds, amines and cyanating agents (viz. HCN, KCN, (EtO)₂P(O)CN, Et₂AlCN, Bu₃SnCN and TMSCN) in the presence of a

wide variety of homogenous and heterogeneous catalysts¹³⁻¹⁶. In continuation to our works on the synthesis and X-ray analysis of promising organic molecules¹⁷, we wish herein to report synthesis, spectroscopic properties and crystal structure of 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile (**1**) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Structure of 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile (**1**).

Results and discussion

The synthesis of the compound i.e. 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile (**1**) is illustrated in Scheme 1. The synthesis of **1** is carried out from 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (**2**), 4-fluoroaniline (**3**) and

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile (**1**) via three-component Strecker reaction.

trimethylsilyl cyanide (TMSCN, **4**) under catalysis as well as solvent-free conditions at room temperature within just 20 min with excellent yield (86%). The workup of the reaction mixture is simple and highly convenient. The title compound (**1**) is characterized by detailed spectral analyses including FT-IR, ^1H , ^{13}C NMR and high resolution mass (see Experimental); the compound (**1**) is also unambiguously confirmed for the first time from X-ray crystallographic analysis (Figs. 2 and 3). Detailed spectral properties and X-ray crystallographic studies for the compound are presented in this article.

Spectroscopic characterization of 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile (1) :

Compound **1** exhibited the characteristic infrared bands at 3350–3320, 3069–3031, 2925–2924, 2250, 1603–1408, 1101–1011 and 735–650 cm^{-1} , respectively for -NH, C-H (Ar-H), -C-H, -CN, C=C (aromatic), C-F, and C-Cl moieties. As expected, two *ortho*-protons with respect to the halogen atom (fluoro-/chloro-) of the aromatic rings are relatively more deshielded than the *meta*-oriented protons and appeared at δ_{H} 7.52 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz) and 7.42 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz) respectively. The methine-proton of amine linkage (-CH(CN)-NH) appeared at δ_{H} 5.34 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz) in its ^1H NMR spectrum, while methine- and cyano-carbon atoms resonate, respectively at δ_{C} 50.49 and 117.76, thereby establishing the structural pattern concerned. The compound showed expected molecular ion peaks in their TOF-MS spectrum at m/z 283.0414 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

X-Ray analysis of 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile (1) :

The crystal structure of compound **1** is shown in Fig. 2¹⁸. The bond lengths and bond angles observed in the structure are comparable with those reported for other related structures. Bond lengths and bond angles are given in Table 2. The C-C bond lengths in the phenyl rings agree well with the literature value¹⁹. The average value of bond angles for all the phenyl rings is 120° . The crys-

tal structure of **1** reveals that whole molecule is essentially planar. The molecules are organized in the crystal lattice forming interpenetrating layers. Weak intermolecular van der Waals interactions are presumably responsible for the stability of molecules in the unit cell.

Fig. 2. ORTEP diagram of compound **1** (CCDC 946073).

Fig. 3. The packing arrangement of molecules viewed down the *a*-axis.

The title compound crystallizes in orthorhombic crystal system with space group Pbcn having following unit-cell parameters : $a = 13.9791(4)$, $b = 6.9972(2)$, $c = 25.0724(6)$ Å and $Z = 8$. The crystal structure of **1** was

Note

solved by employing direct methods using SHELXS97¹⁹ software (Sheldrick, 2008). All non-hydrogen atoms of the molecule were located in the best E-map. Isotropic refinement of the structure by least squares methods using SHELXL97²⁰ was followed by anisotropic refinement of all non-hydrogen atoms²⁰. The values of $R_{\text{int}} = 0.0372$ and $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0162$ show the quality of the data satisfactory. A total of 256 phase sets were refined with the correct phase set having an absolute figure of merit, $M(\text{abs}) = 0.966$ and combined figure of merit $\text{CFOM} = 0.090$. Multi-solution tangent refinement was carried out using 803 E -values with $E > 1.2$. All the H atoms were geometrically fixed and allowed to ride on their parent C atoms with $\text{C-H} = 0.93\text{--}0.98 \text{ \AA}$ and $U_{\text{iso}}(\text{H}) = 1.5 U_{\text{eq}}(\text{C})$ of the attached C atoms for methyl group and $1.2 U_{\text{eq}}$ for other H atoms. Finally, the R -factor converged to 0.0494 for 1992 observed reflections after five cycles of refinement were employed. The residual electron density in the final difference Fourier map ranges from -0.395 to 0.498 e\AA^{-3} . Atomic scattering factors were taken from International Tables for X-ray crystallography²¹. The geometry of the molecule was calculated by using WinGX²², PARST²³ and PLATON²⁴ software's. The crystallographic data is summarized in Table 1. CCDC No. 946073 for the compound **1** contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper²⁵.

Experimental

General: Infrared spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu (FT-IR 8400S) FT-IR spectrophotometer on KBr discs. NMR spectra were obtained at 400 MHz, Bruker DRX spectrometer with CDCl_3 as the solvent. Mass spectra (TOF-MS) were measured on a QTOF Micro mass spectrometer. Melting point was recorded on a Chemiline 726 melting point apparatus and is uncorrected.

General procedure for the preparation of 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile (1):

The synthesis of the title compound was carried out via one-pot catalyst-free Strecker reaction under solvent-free conditions at room temperature. An oven-dried screw cap test tube was charged with a magnetic stir bar, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.140 g, 1 mmol), 4-fluoroaniline

Table 1. Crystal data and other experimental details for compound **1**

Properties	Compound 1
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{ClFN}_2$
Formula weight	260.69
Crystal description	White, Block
Crystal system	Orthorhombic
Space group	Pbcn
Unit cell dimension	$a = 13.9791(4)$ $b = 6.9972(2)$ $c = 25.0724(6) \text{ \AA}$
Crystal size (mm)	$0.30 \times 0.20 \times 0.20$
Unit cell volume (\AA^3)	2452.45(12)
No. of molecules per unit cell (Z)	8
Radiation, wavelength (\AA)	$\text{MoK}\alpha$, 0.71073
Density (calculated) (mg m^{-3})	1.412
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Absorption coefficient (mm^{-1})	0.305
$F(000)$	1072
Scan mode	ω
θ range for entire data collection	3.56 to 29.05°
Range of indices	$-17 \leq h \leq 17$, $-8 \leq k \leq 8$, $-30 \leq l \leq 30$
Reflections collected/unique	32027/2420
Reflections observed ($I > 2\sigma(I)$)	1992
R_{int}	0.0372
R_{sigma}	0.0162
Structure determination	Direct methods
Refinement	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
No. of parameters refined	164
Final R	0.0494
$wR(F^2)$	0.1241
Weight	$1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0434P)^2 + 1.9771P]$ Where $P = [F_o^2 + 2F_c^2]/3$
Goodness-of-fit	1.056
$(\Delta/\sigma)_{\text{max}}$	0.000
Final residual electron density	$-0.395 < \Delta\rho < 0.498 \text{ e\AA}^{-3}$
Measurement	X'calibur system – Oxford diffraction make, UK [Oxford Diffraction, 2010]
Software for structure solution	SHELXS97 ²⁰
Software for refinement	SHELXL97 ²⁰
Software for molecular plotting	ORTEP-3 ²² , PLATON ²³
Software for geometrical calculations	PLATON ²³ , PARST ²⁴

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) for compound **1**

Bond length		Bond angles	
N(4)-H(4)	0.860(2)	H(4)-N(4)-C(12)	120.4(2)
N(4)-C(12)	1.418(3)	H(4)-N(4)-C(5)	120.5(2)
N(4)-C(5)	1.458(3)	C(12)-N(4)-C(5)	119.1(2)
C(12)-C(7)	1.397(4)	N(4)-C(12)-C(7)	119.1(2)
C(12)-C(10)	1.384(4)	N(4)-C(12)-C(10)	122.2(2)
C(5)-H(5)	0.980(3)	C(7)-C(12)-C(10)	118.7(2)
C(5)-C(8)	1.522(3)	N(4)-C(5)-H(5)	108.0(2)
C(5)-C(13)	1.495(4)	N(4)-C(5)-C(8)	110.5(2)
F(2)-C(16)	1.361(3)	N(4)-C(5)-C(13)	111.8(2)
C(8)-C(18)	1.383(4)	H(5)-C(5)-C(8)	108.0(2)
C(8)-C(11)	1.386(4)	H(5)-C(5)-C(13)	108.0(2)
C(18)-H(18)	0.930(3)	C(8)-C(5)-C(13)	110.5(2)
C(18)-C(17)	1.389(3)	C(5)-C(8)-C(18)	120.2(2)
C(17)-H(17)	0.930(3)	C(5)-C(8)-C(11)	120.5(2)
C(17)-C(6)	1.373(4)	C(18)-C(8)-C(11)	119.2(2)
C(13)-N(3)	1.138(4)	C(8)-C(18)-H(18)	119.8(2)
C(7)-H(7)	0.930(3)	C(8)-C(18)-C(17)	120.4(3)
C(7)-C(14)	1.382(4)	H(18)-C(18)-C(17)	119.8(3)
C(6)-C(9)	1.376(4)	C(18)-C(17)-H(17)	120.4(3)
C(6)-C(1)	1.737(3)	C(18)-C(17)-C(6)	119.2(3)
C(11)-H(11)	0.930(3)	H(17)-C(17)-C(6)	120.4(3)
C(11)-C(9)	1.383(4)	C(5)-C(13)-N(3)	179.1(3)
C(14)-H(14)	0.930(3)	C(12)-C(7)-H(7)	119.8(3)
C(14)-C(16)	1.361(4)	C(12)-C(7)-C(14)	120.4(3)
C(16)-C(15)	1.367(4)	H(7)-C(7)-C(14)	119.8(3)
C(15)-H(15)	0.930(3)	C(17)-C(6)-C(9)	121.4(3)
C(15)-C(10)	1.390(4)	C(17)-C(6)-Cl(1)	119.5(2)
C(10)-H(10)	0.930(3)	C(9)-C(6)-Cl(1)	119.0(2)
C(9)-H(9)	0.930(3)	C(8)-C(11)-H(11)	119.6(3)
		C(8)-C(11)-C(9)	120.7(3)
		H(11)-C(11)-C(9)	119.6(3)
		C(7)-C(14)-H(14)	120.4(3)
		C(7)-C(14)-C(16)	119.3(3)
		H(14)-C(14)-C(16)	120.3(3)
		F(2)-C(16)-C(14)	119.1(3)
		F(2)-C(16)-C(15)	118.8(3)
		C(14)-C(16)-C(15)	122.1(3)
		C(16)-C(15)-H(15)	120.6(3)
		C(16)-C(15)-C(10)	118.8(3)
		H(15)-C(15)-C(10)	120.6(3)
		C(12)-C(10)-C(15)	120.6(3)
		C(12)-C(10)-H(10)	119.7(3)
		C(15)-C(10)-H(10)	119.7(3)
		C(6)-C(9)-C(11)	119.0(3)
		C(6)-C(9)-H(9)	120.5(3)
		C(11)-C(9)-H(9)	120.5(3)

(0.111 g, 1 mmol) and trimethylsilyl cyanide (TMSCN, 0.109 g, 1.1 mmol) in sequential manner; the reaction mixture was then stirred vigorously at room temperature¹⁶. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC, and on completion just after 20 min, 20 ml of distilled water was added to the reaction mixture with constant stirring for another 10 min. The solid residue obtained on simple filtration was then recrystallized from aqueous ethanol (80 : 20) to afford pure 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile.

2-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile (**1**): White solid; yield 86%; m.p. 102–104 °C; R_f 0.4210 (PE : EtOAc 90 : 10); $[\alpha]_D^{28} = \pm 0.0$ ($c = 1$, CHCl_3); IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3351, 3125, 2938, 2250, 1625, 1509, 1487, 1242, 1228, 1097, 1017, 834, 826, 699, 655 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 7.52 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.42 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.97 (2H, t, J 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.72–6.69 (2H, m, Ar-H), 5.34 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, $-\text{CH}(\text{CN})-\text{NH}-$), 3.95 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, $-\text{CH}(\text{CN})-\text{NH}-$); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 158.50, 156.60, 140.63, 140.61, 135.72, 132.24, 129.58, 128.59, 117.76 ($-\text{CN}$), 116.33, 116.15, 115.98, 115.92, 50.49. TOF-MS: Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{ClFN}_2\text{Na}$ 283.0414 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$; Found: 283.0418. For crystallization 50 mg of compound dissolved in 10 ml aqueous ethanol (80 : 20) and left for several days at ambient temperature which yielded white block shaped crystals.

Single crystal X-ray diffraction studies :

X-Ray intensity data of 32027 reflections (of which 2420 unique) in case of **1** was collected on X'calibur Computer-Controlled Single Crystal X-ray Diffractometer having CCD Camera. CCD area-detector diffractometer equipped with graphite monochromated $\text{MoK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å). The crystals used for data collection was of dimensions 0.30 × 0.20 × 0.20 mm. The cell dimensions were determined by least-squares fit of angular settings of 13042 reflections in the θ range 3.55 to 28.98°. The intensities were measured by ω scan mode for θ ranges 3.56 to 26.00°. A total number of 32027 reflections were recorded of which 2420 reflections were found unique with index range: $-17 \leq h \leq 17$, $-8 \leq k \leq 8$, $-30 \leq l \leq 30$. The number of reflections after applying the limiting criterion $[I > 2\sigma(I)]$ converged to 1992 which

were considered as observed. The reflection data were corrected for Lorentz and polarization effects.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have synthesized an α -aminonitrile via a rapid and eco-friendly way under both catalyst- and solvent-free conditions with excellent yield at room temperature. A detailed X-ray crystallographic study of its unit crystal is also documented.

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25. Supplementary Crystallographic data for the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC No. 946073 for the compound 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(4-fluorophenylamino)acetonitrile (**1**). Copy of this information may be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.